

ON THE CREOLIZATIVE STUDY OF THE INDIVIDUAL IN THE TEXT

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Later, a number of studies are being carried out in the field of linguistics, like in other disciplines. Such research is characterized by the breadth of scope, the variety of possibilities of linguistic and nonlinear expression. At the moment, trends in the approach to the evidence of the language under study from different points of view are observed. This is serving the formation of new directions in science or fields. Research within textual linguistics in linguistics is regularly expanding at the expense of new directions such as linguopoetics, Psycholinguistics, pragmatics, Stylistics, linguoculturology, cognitology and Sociolinguistics. In the process of communication, the approach to the means of expressing the interaction of speech participants in terms of the functions of the anthropocentric paradigm serves to form new directions in linguistics. In research on textual research, problems related to personality traits can be recognized as pressing issues of linguistics.

The research carried out in these directions is carried out with reference to the achievements of traditional linguistics. This requires a new perspective and a unique approach to work of an early pictorial nature about the tools of linguistic and nonlinear expression. One such area is the dialogue between people in relation to their daily lifestyle and issues aimed at studying its different forms of expression. Under the concepts of different forms of expression, words, gestures and other means of information expression are meant. There is a need to analyze and research these tools as integrated elements of a complex or communication process system, these issues are referred to in the language as a creolizative structure. In the scientific literature, it is noted that in the process of communication and intervention, the occurrence of communicative acts is carried out through a system of various signs. In particular, they are manifested in "details" related to verbal, nonverbal or speech situation. Therefore, such means of expression belonging to a semiotic system with a communicative status that serves to express information in itself form a paradigm of contradictory linguistic and nonlinear (extralinguistic) units. On the basis of this paradigm, it can be said that the composition of nonlinear units formed by a semiotic concept in itself is also enriched at the expense of details in the process of speech. The details are among the tools that provide excellent information about speakers. They serve to express personality traits such as words and gestures. To the extent that such characteristics as psyche, character, worldview, imagination and national mentality inherent in speech participants are manifested in the language that is considered the basis of communication, the leading components of contact communication are also visible to this extent in the listed gestures and details. The contextual paradigm of such units, which form a holistic system of communication, based on a denotative structure, and their functions that serve to express personality traits, has not been the object of Special Research. It seems that the structure of the text on which the basis of

communication is considered does not consist only of one medium or form, but also its composition is formed from all units of expression associated with the verbal, nonverbal, contextual situation. The formation of the character of the hero by the writer and the achievement of his perception in the reader's imagination as a complex image or as a positive and negative hero, of course, depends on the variety, variety of means of expression. All this in a holistic way serves to ensure that the dialogue of speakers or heroes of the work is effective and the image of the character that the writer refers to in the work of art. Research related to such a complex structure of communication serves to fill the gap in linguistics regarding the theory of communication as new areas of science. As noted in the scientific literature, "...the issue of the attitude of extralinguistic and intralinguistic factors has always and fundamentally been considered one of the most fundamental issues in linguistics." It seems that the process of communication or the composition of the text is complicated by different forms of expression. They serve as means of expression to illuminate the communicative purpose of speech participants. In order to scientifically substantiate the views on this, it is necessary to focus on field research. The work involved in poetic textual linguistics, which is occurring today in Russian and European linguistics, is characterized precisely by the mixed application of means of expression and its focus on revealing their functions. Studies of a different nature regarding the visual text and its structure are prominent in these works. In this regard, K.Sluskaya, G.Eiger, W.L.Yuxt, R.Jacobson, L.Bolshyanova, A.Mikheev, A.Bernaskaya, Yu.Sorokin, E.The research of linguists such as Tarasov on the complex structure of the text opens the way for our new research in the field of creolizative-structural research of the image of personality characteristics in the artistic text. In the work of scientists whose names are noted above, one can also apply to the study of texts within the framework of linguistic and nonlinear forms of expression of term and terminological units, which refer to a completely new direction of linguistics, such as "polycode texts", "syncretic messages", "isoverbal complex", "creolized texts". The context is complicated by contradictory verbal and nonverbal parts, which can also be named by the expression of concepts such as polycode structure, blurred message, isoverbal complex, creolized structure. It is important that the text formed in the integrity of linguistic and nonlinear means on the basis of concepts expressed through terminological units is studied as a special object of study. The process of communication between speakers is not only expressed only by the elements of a single linguistic system itself, but also by non-linguistic units that are language-friendly, such as exchange of ideas, transmission of information. This serves to ensure that information is complete and perfect as well as the proper perception of personality traits. The colorfulness of the means of expression does not only represent the communicative purpose or information that speakers are referring to. In addition to generating verbal and nonverbal acts, each linguistic or nonlinear system unit that speech participants use in the process of communication also serves to represent characteristics of the person of the speakers. This feature is inherent in any language system and is manifested in all acts of the same language. Therefore, any language reflects the customs, national values, culture of that nation. This is evidenced by the fact that the languages of the peoples of the world have a unique coding system. The coding system is fully reflected not only in the language, but also in other means of expression that provide support in the process of speech communication. Elements of the nonlinear system are also recognized as a special coding system that reflects the urgency, value and culture of the nation. The communication process is carried out using these few

coding system elements. This sets the stage for the manifestation of characters or personality traits in the process of communication, which occurs with the help of various system elements. In general, while the means of expression serve to show personality traits in one aspect, at the same time, in the second aspect, the language of the nation and its other means of expression serve to express the specific mentality, culture, tradition of that people. This is referred to as the national-cultural encoding of means of expression in the language of science. This was stated by professor A.Nurmonov's views confirm the above points. In particular, " Herman Wembury was a famous Orientalist scholar who knew not only Arabic, Persian, Uzbek, but also the culture, customs of these peoples. Therefore, he surrounds the turban and enters between the peoples of Iran and Central Asia, disguised as Mullah. From his treatment, from what he says, it is completely imperceptible that he is a Foreign, a vulgar. As a connoisseur of Islam, the history and culture of the peoples of the East, he gains respect and attention among the population. But in one sitting, impressed by the very pleasant music, involuntarily begins to shake his leg, looking at the rhythm of the melody. This action reveals to the people of the circle that he is foreign. Because among the peoples of the East, the sign of pleasure from singing was not expressed by the movement of the foot, but by the gradual vibration of the head in a horizontal position." The definition given to Herman Wemberi serves to reveal other folk-specific features along with the expression of the language and culture of the peoples of the East, such as its language, the salla associated with dress, and other means of expression such as detail, gestures and movements. It would seem that if each element or means of expression in a text is recognized as a code in isolation, concepts such as the code of linguistic units, the code of nonlinear units, the code of nonverbal expressions can be generalized as a kind of semiotic system. So, even in fiction, the process of communication between a writer and his characters is carried out through various means of expression. Participants in speech communication equally use the same linguistic and nonlinear means as the heroes of the work of art in the process of mutual exchange of ideas. On this basis, it can be said that the process of communication is carried out not only on the basis of one type of coding system units, but also through codes related to different systems. It is seen that the dicodized tools can be used in the process of communication compensatedly, performing a specific communicative function related to personality traits and unlocking the character of the characters.

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